

Table 2 DNA glycosylases: SNPs, function and disease

Protein	Protein Variant	DNA Polymorphisms	Functional consequences	Diseases	References
UNG	Arg88Cys	rs151095402	Defect in RPA binding and ssDNA recruitment	Colorectal cancer	102, 103
	Intron variant	rs3219218 A/G	n.d	Rheumatoid arthritis	107
	Intron variant	rs246079 G/A	n.d	Decreased risk of esophageal squamous cell carcinoma;	105
	Intron variant	rs246079 G/A	n.d	Rheumatoid arthritis	107
	Upstream gene variant	rs2337395	n.d	Age-related macular degeneration	106
SMUG1	Intron variant	rs34259	n.d	Ovarian Cancer	104
	5'UTR variant	rs3087404	n.d.	Age-related macular degeneration	106
	Regulatory region variant	rs202916	n.d.	ESCC	114
TDG	Val367Met	rs2888805	n.d.	NMSC	113
	Arg66Gly	rs369649741	n.d	Colorectal cancer	103
	Intron variants	rs4135054	n.d.	Esophageal squamous cell carcinoma	110,114
	Intron variant	rs167715	n.d.	Ovarian cancer (with BRCA1 mutation)	104
	Intron variant	rs4135087	n.d	Ovarian cancer (with BRCA1 mutation)	104
MBD4	Asp568His	rs2307293	Reduced binding and catalytic activity	Gastric cancer	4,116
	Cys61Arg	rs2307296	Reduced binding and catalytic activity	Gastric cancer	4,116
	Glu346Lys	rs140693,	n.d.	Esophageal squamous cell carcinoma	118
	Glu346Lys	rs140693	n.d.	Lung cancer	120,121
	Glu346Lys	rs140693	n.d.	Cervical cancer	119
OGG1	Ser326Cys	rs1052133	Reduced DNA repair under oxidizing conditions; genetic instability; inhibition of nucleolar localization	Lung cancer; non small cell carcinoma; squamous cell carcinoma; adenocarcinoma;	124-128 133-139
				Breast cancer	140,141
				Ovarian cancer	142
				Colorectal cancer	146-149
				Bladder cancer	150,151
				Hepatocellular carcinoma	153
				Nasopharyngeal carcinoma	156-159

Protein	Protein Variant	DNA Polymorphisms	Functional consequences	Diseases	References
				Prostate cancer	160
		In association with XRCC1		Cholangiocarcinoma	154
				Myelodysplastic syndrome	161
				Oral cavity, larynx and pharynx (protettivo)	155
				Cataract	165,166
				Age-Related Macular Degeneration	167
				Noise-Induced Hearing Loss	169
				Coronary ectasia	180
				Coronary artery disease	179
				Huntington Disease	170-171
				Alzheimer Disease	173,174
				Cognitive performance	175
	Upstream gene variant	rs159153	n.d.	Colorectal cancer	152
	Intron variant	rs2072668	n.d.	Breast cancer	144
	Non coding transcript exon variant	rs2304277	hOGG1 downregulation	Ovarian cancer	104, 143
MUTYH	5'UTR variant	rs3219472	n.d.	Cholangiocarcinoma	199
	Arg260Gln		Defective adenine DNA glycosylase activity	Cholangiocarcinoma	200
	His434Asp		Defective adenine DNA glycosylase activity	Cholangiocarcinoma	200
	AluYb8MUT YH	rs10527342	Increased genomic 8-oxoG; reduced mitochondrial protein expression; decreased mitochondrial homeostasis	Breast and gastric cancer	195-197
	Gln324His	rs3219489	Reduced affinity for Hus1;	Colorectal cancer;	192-194
			n.d.	Lung cancer	191
	Intron variant	rs 3219493	n.d	Bladder cancer	198
NEIL1	Upstream variant	rs4462560	n.d	Myelodysplastic syndrome	161
	Gly83Asp	rs5745906	Defective DNA glycosylase activity	Primary sclerosing cholangitis Cholangiocarcinoma	200,201
Protein	Protein Variant	DNA Polymorphisms	Functional consequences	Diseases	References
NEIL2	Upstream	rs1466785	n.d.	Breast cancer (with	104

Lori 11/22/y 12:09 PM

Commenta [1]: Questi lavori mostrano che non c'è associazione con Alzheimer. Forse va scitto?

gene variant r			BRCA1/2 mutation)		
	Pro123Thr	rs8191666	n.d.	Colorectal cancer	103
	Arg103Gln	rs8191613	No defective DNA Repair No lower affinity for Pol β	Lung cancer	205
	5'UTR variant	rs804270	n.d.	Gastric cancer	206
	Arg257Leu	rs8191664	Defective DNA repair Lower affinity for Pol β	Lung cancer	205
NEIL3	Intron variant	rs6850861	n.d.	Fasting insulin level Overweight and type 2 diabetes	211
	Intron variant	rs6823018	n.d.	Fasting insulin level Overweight and type 2 diabetes	211
	Intron variant	rs6830266	n.d.	Fasting insulin level Overweight and type 2 diabetes	211
	Intron variant	rs2048077	n.d.	Fasting insulin level Overweight and type 2 diabetes	211
	Intron variant	rs12645561	n.d.	Glioma Glioblastoma	208,209
	Intron variant	rs12645561	n.d.	Myocardial infarction	210
	Intergenic variant	rs1983132	n.d.	Prostate cancer	207